

Solute-Solvent Interactions in Solutions of Some Ammonium Salts in Aqueous Dioxane

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Solute-solvent interactions are reported in the concentration range from the conductance studies of N_4HCl , NH_4Br and NH_4NO_3 in 10, 20 and 30 weight per cent. of Dioxane-water mixtures at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40°. Experimental data were analysed for limiting equivalent conductance, Λ_0 , on the basis of Owen's method. An attempt is made to discuss the results in terms of solute-solvent interaction from the temperature-coefficient of the Walden product, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ of the electrolyte solutions. Further, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ is also found to exhibit a linear relationship with the dielectric constant, D , of the dioxane-water mixtures.

FREQUENT use of non-aqueous solvents as media for organic and inorganic reactions has led to increasing interest in the transport properties of electrolytes in solution. Electrolyte behaviour in solutions is revealed by conductance and viscosity investigations which elucidate directly from experimental measurements the nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions. Recently, there have been a number of studies on conductance of electrolytes in many non-aqueous solvents like DMSO^{1,2}, Sulfolane³, Acetonitrile⁴, Acetone⁵, Methyl-ethylketone⁶, tetramethylurea⁷, aliphatic alcohols⁸ and Ethyleneglycol⁹, etc. Conductance measurements in binary mixed solvents have also been widely used for the investigations of solute-solvent interactions in electrolyte solutions. Fuoss *et al.* have extensively studied the conductance behaviour of tetraalkylammonium salts in various binary mixed solvents, namely, MeOH-benzene¹⁰, MeOH-methyl-ethylketone¹¹, MeOH- CCl_4 ¹², EtOH- CCl_4 ¹² and dioxane-water^{14,15} mixtures. Conductance of some alkali halides in dioxane-water have also been reported recently by Fuoss *et al.*¹⁶.

The present study has been carried out with a view to: (i) report the limiting equivalent conductivities of some ammonium salts in dioxane-water mixtures and to (ii) study the temperature coefficient of the Walden product, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ and (iii) its variation with the dielectric constant of the dioxane-water mixtures.

Experimental

Electrolytes *viz.*, NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and NH_4NO_3 , in the present study, were of Analar grade and were used as such without further purification.

Dioxane (G. R.) was purified by refluxing over sodium for 6 hours followed by distillation. The specific conductance for the purified dioxane was found to be negligible. Water of specific conductance

1.3×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ was used for making, by weight, the aqueous mixtures of dioxane.

All solutions were made by weight and conversion of the molality to molarity was done by using the usual relationship¹⁷.

Conductance measurements were carried out at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40°, in the manner similar so that reported in our earlier publications.¹⁸⁻²⁰

Results and Discussion

The derived parameters, limiting equivalent conductances, Λ_0 and the Walden products, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ for the electrolytes in dioxane-water mixtures of different compositions, and at different temperatures, are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE-1 VALUES OF Λ_0 AND $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ FOR NH_4Cl , NH_4Br AND NH_4NO_3 IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Weight per cent., Dioxane	Electrolyte	Temperature (°C)	Λ_0 (S.cm ² .mol ⁻¹)	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$ (S.mol. ⁻¹ N.S.10 ⁻⁶)	
10	NH_4Cl	25	99.50	1.298	
		30	141.50	1.255	
		35	156.70	1.273	
		40	180.50	1.291	
20	NH_4Cl	40	147.49	1.385	
		30	NH_4Cl	128.50	1.445
			NH_4Br	114.05	1.420
			NH_4NO_3	151.07	1.340
30	NH_4Br	35	156.52	1.271	
		40	167.50	1.190	
		20	NH_4Br	151.00	1.420
			NH_4Br	140.50	1.580
10	NH_4NO_3	25	115.50	1.438	
		30	165.16	1.465	
		35	176.50	1.492	
		40	208.67	1.520	
20	NH_4NO_3	40	173.10	1.625	
		30	169.50	1.794	

Δ_0 values for the electrolytes in dioxane-water mixtures were estimated from a method proposed by Owen²¹. This is based on the conductance equation :

$$\Delta = \Delta_0 - SC^{\frac{1}{2}} + A \log c + Bc \quad \dots (1)$$

Where Δ is the observed equivalent conductance at the concentration C , S refers to the limiting Onsager slope, A and B are the constants.

For extrapolation purposes, equation (1) is written as :

$$\frac{\Delta + SC^{\frac{1}{2}}}{C} - \Delta_0 = A \log c + B \quad \dots (2)$$

so that when the left-hand side is plotted against $\log c$, a straight line will result if the correct value of Δ_0 has been chosen. This choice is made by trial and error. The values of Δ_0 for the electrolytes in aqueous mixtures of dioxane, which gave the best straight lines according to relation (2), were

therefore estimated and these have been recorded in the Table 1.

Viscosities of the aqueous mixtures of dioxane, η_0 for the evaluation of Walden products, $\Delta_0 \eta_0$ are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE-2 VISCOSITIES OF DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Weight Per cent., Dioxane	Temperature (°C)	Viscosity $10^4 \cdot \eta_0$ (N.S.m ⁻²)
10	25	12.45
	30	8.87
	35	8.12
	40	7.15
20	40	9.39
	40	11.25

Variations of Walden product with Temperature :

Experimental data for the temperature variation of the Walden product of electrolytes in aqueous

solutions and in organic solvents are scanty. Only a few studies on the variation of Walden product with temperature in aqueous solutions and in organic solvents^{20,23}, have recently, been reported in the literature.

Structural effects on the conductance of ions in aqueous solutions are derived by a comparison of their Walden products in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions and at different temperatures and pressure²⁴⁻²⁶. Thus in the case of large Walden products, their negative temperature coefficients²⁷, have been attributed to decrease in the structure of the solvent, which can be attributed to the structure-breaking characteristic of the electrolyte in the solvent, whereas positive temperature coefficient have been attributed to the increase in the structure of the solvent which in turn refers to the structure-making characteristic of the electrolyte.

$\Delta_o\eta_o$ versus $t(^{\circ}\text{C})$ plots for NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and NH_4NO_3 in aqueous dioxane (10% by weight) are found to be linear as shown in Figure 1(a).

Positive temperature coefficients of the Walden products for NH_4Cl and NH_4NO_3 in 10% dioxane-water mixture shown in Figure 1(a), can, therefore, be attributed to the structure-making characteristic of these electrolytes in this mixture. Further, structure-making has also been attributed to positive solvation²⁸, whereas the structure-breaking has been attributed to the negative solvation of the electrolytes in the solvent. Greater positive slope of the $\Delta_o\eta_o$ vs. $t(^{\circ}\text{C})$ plot for NH_4NO_3 than NH_4Cl in 10% dioxane-water mixture suggests that NH_4NO_3 acts as a better structure promotor than NH_4Cl in this mixture or in other words, positive solvation is greater in NH_4NO_3 solutions of 10% dioxane-water than NH_4Cl solutions in the same solvent mixture. The greater structure-making in case of NH_4NO_3 than NH_4Cl can be attributed to the fact that NO_3^- ion being smaller in size than the corresponding Cl^- ion (NH_4^+ being common) fits well into the vacant sites²⁹ of the solvent matrix.

$\Delta_o\eta_o$ versus $t(^{\circ}\text{C})$ plots in Figure 1(a) show a negative temperature coefficient in case of NH_4Br solutions in 10% dioxane-water mixture. This suggests that it acts as a structure-breaker in this mixture or in other words, negative solute-solvent interaction is predicted in NH_4Br solutions. This decrease in the structure of the solvent in this case can be attributed to the greater ionic³⁰ size of Br^- ion than both the Cl^- and NO_3^- ions.

From, Figure 1(b) it is also observed that the plots of Walden product. $\Delta_o\eta_o$ for NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and NH_4NO_3 solutions in aqueous mixtures of dioxane (10, 20 and 30% by weight at 40°) versus the dielectric constant. D . of these mixtures are linear.

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